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Nucleotide cytokinins are more efficient than their free-base counterparts in promoting rice seedling growth

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A previous study (Hsieh and Tung 2001) has shown that cytokinin and related compounds such as adenine (Ade), adenosine monophosphate (AMP), and dihydrozeatin (DHZ) can effectively promote seedling growth of rice (cv. Tai-keng 3) in the summer. In this study, we found that nucleotide cytokinins such as benzyladenosine 5-monophosphate (BARMP), zeatin ribonucleoside (ZR), zeatin ribonucleoside 5-monophosphate (ZRMP), and dihydrozeatin ribonucleoside 5-monophosphate (DHZRMP) are more effective than their free-base counterparts in promoting seedling growth in Tai-keng 3.

Rice seeds were surface-sterilized with 10% NaOCl for 10 min, rinsed with distilled water a few times, and placed under white fluorescent lamps (20 m mol m⁻² s⁻¹) for germination at 26 °C in the summer. Distilled water was replaced daily. Germinating rice seeds (5-d-old) were transferred to culture solutions that include Hoagland solution [Ca(NO₃)₂, 5.0

× 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; KNO₃, 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; MgSO₄, 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; KH₂PO₄, 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol L⁻¹; Fe-EDTA, 1.18 × 10⁻⁵ mol L⁻¹ and micronutrient solution consisting of H₃BO₃, 4.6 × 10⁻⁵ mol L⁻¹; MnCl₂ · 4H₂O, 9.14 × 10⁻⁶ mol L⁻¹; ZnSO₄ · 4H₂O, 7.65 × 10⁻⁷ mol L⁻¹; CuSO₄, 7.0 × 10⁻⁷ mol L⁻¹; and H₂MoO₄, 1.24 × 10⁻⁷ mol L⁻¹; pH 5.0] and Hoagland solution in which BA, BARMP, DHZ, DHZRMP, Z, and ZRMP each were added to make concentrations from 10⁻⁹ to 10⁻¹⁷ mol, respectively. A group of concentrations from each test chemical solution was tested each time and poured into plastic trays (diam 11.5 cm, depth 3.5 cm) with two pieces of filter paper (Whatman No. 1, diam 9.0 cm) each. Each test concentration contained four replicates. At least 15 germinating seeds in each tray were grown under white fluorescent lamps (20.0 m mol m⁻² s⁻¹) for another 13 d at 26 °C. The test solution in each tray was maintained at a sufficient level for seedlings to absorb enough nutrition during the experiment pe-

riod. At harvest, rice seedlings from each tray were washed with water (mainly for roots) and blotted with paper tissue. Seed was cut off from each seedling. Shoots were then separated from roots and each portion was dried in an oven at 70 °C for 24 h. Dried shoots and roots from each tray were weighed separately to provide a unit of dry mass. Results of measured values from a group of concentrations of each test chemical solution were analyzed by Duncan's multiple range test at the 5% level.

Results (Table 1) showed that nucleotide cytokinins are more effective than their free-base cytokinins in promoting rice seedling shoot growth: ZRMP worked at 10⁻¹² to 10⁻¹¹ M, whereas trans-zeatin (tZ) did not from 10⁻¹⁶ to 10⁻⁹ M; BARMP did at 10⁻¹³ to 10⁻¹¹ M, whereas BA did not at 10⁻¹¹ to 10⁻¹⁰; DHRMP did at 10⁻¹⁶ M, whereas DHZ did not at below 10⁻¹⁵ M. Reasons for these different ranges of optimal concentrations between nucleotide cytokinin and its free-base

Table 1. Effect of free-base and nucleotide cytokinins on the growth of rice seedling shoots, dry shoot weight (mg plant⁻¹).

Compound	Concentration (M)									
	0	10 ⁻¹⁷	10 ⁻¹⁶	10 ⁻¹⁵	10 ⁻¹⁴	10 ⁻¹³	10 ⁻¹²	10 ⁻¹¹	10 ⁻¹⁰	10 ⁻⁹
tZ	11.2 ± 0.1 a						10.6 ± 0.3 cd	10.5 ± 0.1 d	10.8 ± 0.2 bcd	11.3 ± 0 a
	10.6 ± 0.0 a		11 ± 0.1 a	11 ± 0.1 a	10.4 ± 0.0a	10.5 ± 0.0 a				
ZRMP	10.7 ± 0.2 b					11.1 ± 0.3 b	11.7 ± 0.2 a	11.7 ± 0.2 a		
BA	9.7 ± 0.2 b						9.8 ± 0.2 b	10.5 ± 0.1 a	10.7 ± 0.1 a	10.1 ± 0.2 b
BARMP	10.0 ± 0.3 b					10.4 ± 0.2 a	10.6 ± 0.1 a	10.5 ± 0.4 a		
DHZ	10.7 ± 0.2 b						11.7 ± 0.1 a	12.0 ± 0.1 a	12.0 ± 0.1 a	11.7 ± 0.1 a
	10.6 ± 0.2 b		11.3 ± 0.3 b	11.4 ± 0.2 a	11.6 ± 0.3 a	11.5 ± 0.0a				
DHZRMP	9.9 ± .01 b	10.4 ± 0.2 b	10.7 ± 0.2 a	10.4 ± 0.2 b						

tZ = trans-zeatin, ZRMP = zeatin ribonucleoside 5-monophosphate, BA = benzyladenine, BARMP = benzyladenosine 5-monophosphate, DHZ = dihydrozeatin, DHZRMP = dihydrozeatin ribonucleoside 5-monophosphate. Free-base cytokinins = tZ, BA, and DHZ; nucleotide cytokinins = ZRMP, BARMP, and DHZRMP. Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different. Growth period = May to September. In this table, each chemical treatment contained two separate experiments (the upper-row data were from one group of concentrations; the lower-row data were from another group of concentrations).

counterparts are not known at present. Reasons are possibly different mechanisms of absorption and translocation or disparate actions on gene expression. Table 2 shows that, in root growth of rice seedlings, BARMP at 10^{-12} to 10^{-11} M and DHZRMP at 10^{-16} mol

were effective, whereas others were not. From these results, it can be concluded that nucleotide cytokinins are more efficient than their free-base counterparts in promoting rice seedling growth because a lower concentration is needed to promote growth.

Reference

Hsieh MC, Tung MS. 2001. Adenine, adenosine monophosphate, and cytokinin: nutrients for rice seedling growth in the summer crop. *Int. Rice Res. Notes* 26(2):65-66.

Table 2. Effect of free-base and nucleotide cytokinins on the growth of rice seedling roots, dry root weight (mg plant⁻¹).

Compound	Concentration (M)									
	0	10^{-17}	10^{-16}	10^{-15}	10^{-14}	10^{-13}	10^{-12}	10^{-11}	10^{-10}	10^{-9}
tZ	3.4 ± 0.1 a						3.3 ± 0.1 b	3.2 ± 0.1 a	3.6 ± 0.1 a	3.6 ± 0.1 a
	3.8 ± 0.0 a		4.0 ± 0.1 a	3.8 ± 0.0 a	3.8 ± 0.0 a	3.7 ± 0.0 a				
ZRMP	2.7 ± 0.1 a					2.8 ± 0.1 a	3.1 ± 0 a	3.1 ± 0.1 a		
BA	3.5 ± 0.1 a						3.1 ± 0.1 b	3.3 ± 0.1 a	3.3 ± 0.1 a	3.2 ± 0.1 a
BARMP	2.9 ± 0.1 b					3.0 ± 0.1 b	3.3 ± 0.1 a	3.1 ± 0.1 a		
DHZ	3.3 ± 0.0 a						3.3 ± 0.1 a	3.3 ± 0.0 a	3.3 ± 0.1 a	3.4 ± 0.0 a
	3.6 ± 0.0 a		3.6 ± 0.1 a	3.4 ± 0.1 a	3.4 ± 0.0 a	3.5 ± 0.1 a				
DHZRMP	3.0 ± 0.0 b	3.2 ± 0.1 b	3.4 ± 0.1 a	3.3 ± 0.1 b						

Free cytokinins = tZ, BA, and DHZ. Nucleotide cytokinins = ZRMP, BARMP, and DHZRMP. Values followed by the same letter are not significantly different. In this table, each chemical treatment contained two separate experiments (the upper-row data were from one group of concentrations; the lower-row data were from another group of concentrations).

Maintaining predawn leaf water potential in two upland rice cultivars during drought stress and recovery

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Differences in leaf water potential (LWP) among indica, japonica, and aus rice are possibly due to the magnitude or activity of the root system, and are assumed to result from a difference in root system extent (O'Toole and Cruz 1980). Measuring LWP at predawn, when the plant water potential more closely approaches equilibrium with the water potential of the soil around the roots, is likely to provide a measure of the effects of long-term water stress (Jones 1990). Root length density (RLD) is often used to characterize root system development of rice cultivars because its distribution in the root system is an important indicator of the potential of water uptake. This study care-

fully examined predawn LWP during a period of water exclusion and during recovery with root system development measured through relative RLD.

A greenhouse study was conducted at Kyoto University, Japan, using two upland rice cultivars: Senshou, a Japanese japonica, and IRAT13, also a japonica, which originated from Côte d'Ivoire. Eight pre-germinated seeds (with radicles emerged already) were sown directly in 100-cm-long PVC pot-type microlysimeter setups, an application of the Marriot system designed by Horie and Sakuradani (1982). Each pot, cut in 10-cm layer depth segments, was sealed with strong, transparent plastic tape,

preventing leakage of water. Pots were filled with clean fine sand and fertilized with 2.2 g of NPK fertilizer (14-14-14) mixed thoroughly in 30-cm layers. The experiment used a factorial randomized complete block design with three replications. Seedlings were thinned to six per pot 2 wk after sowing. Pots were kept flooded to 2-3-cm depth above the soil surface. Flooding started 14 d after sowing (DAS). At 62 DAS, two water-level treatments—drought stress and the well-watered control—were employed. Pots assigned to the drought-stress treatment were drained for 4 h and the height of the water was set to 30 cm from the bottom (60-cm depth from the